

Dissociation Constants of 5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline and its Fe(II) Complex in Methanol-Water and Ethanol-Water Mixtures

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The dissociation constants of *tris*-5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline Fe(II) complex have been determined in different methanol-water and ethanol-water mixtures. The role of solvents on the dissociation constants has been discussed in the light of solvent-basicity and ion-solvent interactions. The limitations have also been stressed.

THE *tris*-complex of iron(II) with 1,10-phenanthroline is well-known for its analytical applications. The effects of substitution on 1,10-phenanthroline have been relatively little studied. Brandt and Gullstrom¹, Banks and Bystroff², Lahiri and Aditya³ studied the dissociation constants and other thermodynamic properties of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline and its iron complexes. However, no such studies have been made in mixed solvents.

The effect of solvents like methanol+water and ethanol+water on the dissociations constants of the reactions

(A = 2,2'-bipyridyl ; 1,10-phenanthroline)

have been well studied⁴⁻⁹. The dissociation constants for reaction (1) in case of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline in MeOH-H₂O and EtOH-H₂O mixtures have been determined by Ram, Mandal and Lahiri⁹. We, therefore consider it desirable to study the reactions (2) and (3) for 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline in MeOH-H₂O and EtOH-H₂O mixtures as it may provide some idea regarding the effect of solvents on the substituted ligands and their complexes.

Experimental

The purification of ethanol and methanol, their weight-percentages and dielectric constants were determined in the way described earlier⁴⁻⁹. The traces of water, if any, in the organic solvents were neglected. The solvents were utilised within 24 hr.

5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline (B. D. H.) was used. An weighed amount of ferrous ammonium sulphate was dissolved in a known amount of HClO₄ (G. R., E. Merck) and iron(II) content of the sample was estimated titrimetrically using standard K₂Cr₂O₇ solution. The chemicals used were E. Merck, G. R. grade.

Ferrous *tris*-5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline complex, known as nitroferroin, has an absorption maximum at 510 nm. The addition of methanol and ethanol has no effect on the absorption maximum.

Under our experimental conditions, Fe(n-Ph)₃²⁺ was assumed to be the sole species formed without any Fe(n-Ph)₂⁺ or Fe(n-Ph)₂²⁺¹⁰. The extinction coefficients of nitroferroin at 500 and 510 nm were determined from the optical density readings of solutions containing 10-20 fold excess of ligands to different amounts of ferrous ion where complete conversion of Fe²⁺ to Fe(n-Ph)₃²⁺ took place.

The extinction coefficients of the complex in different mixed solvents are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS OF 5-NITROFERROIN AT DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES OF MeOH-H₂O AND EtOH-H₂O MIXTURES

Wt% of alcohol	Temp. = 25°	
	Extinction coefficients	
	500 nm	510 nm
	MeOH + H ₂ O	
8.0	11143	11416
16.0	12423	12687
25.2	12656	12920
34.4	12249	12482
44.7	12136	12352
54.2	12525	12883
64.1	12455	12729
75.9	11813	12076
	EtOH + H ₂ O	
8.0	12560	12725
16.4	12949	13122
25.3	12605	12769
34.4	11186	11360
44.0	12180	12444
54.1	11343	11452
64.7	12076	12168
76.0	11252	11318

For the determination of stability constants of nitroferroin in mixed solvents, optical densities of solutions containing different amounts of Fe²⁺ ion

($8 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $20 \times 10^{-5} M$) and 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline ($8 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $30 \times 10^{-5} M$) were measured at 500 and 510 nm. The average values of the concentrations of the complex were determined from these measurements. The H^+ ion concentrations of the solutions ranged from $8 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $20 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Spectrophotometric readings were taken with a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer maintained at 25°.

Results and Discussion

In view of the limitations of determining the thermodynamic dissociation constants using "inert electrolytes", it is always desirable to use very dilute solutions so that the activity coefficients can be taken to be unity^{1,2}. In mixed solvents the changes in activity coefficients are due to (i) salt effect (f_i) and (ii) medium effect (f_m)^{1,2}.

Thus, the use of low ionic strengths are particularly important in mixed solvents so that $f_i \rightarrow 1$, i.e. salt effect¹ is eliminated enabling one to study the "medium effect".

The use of "inert electrolyte" is carefully avoided as the solute-solvent interactions of unknown magnitude are likely to mask the "medium effect" for which the reactions are actually studied. Moreover, the relative magnitudes of different types of interactions are difficult to estimate.

Thus the equilibrium constants

$$K_a = \frac{C_{Fe^{2+}} \times C_{n-PhH^+}}{C_{Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+}} \times C_{n-Ph}^2}$$

for reaction (2) have been calculated from the equations

$$[n-PhH^+] = [n-Ph]_T - 3[Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+}] - [n-Ph],$$

$$pK_T = pH + \log \frac{[n-PhH^+]}{[n-Ph]}$$

$$\text{and } [Fe^{2+}]_{free} = [Fe^{2+}]_T - [Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+}]$$

The pK_T values had been previously reported⁹.

We have already discussed^{4,5} the difficulty in the measurement of H^+ ion concentrations in mixed solvents containing the complexes and protonated ligands. In our previous communications^{4,5}, we showed the extent of deviations in the equilibrium constant K_a using the theoretically calculated $[H^+]$ and experimentally determined $[H^+]$ using appropriate corrections^{1,3,14} for the changes in solvent compositions. The differences are expected as the corrected H^+ ion concentrations take into account the changes in the medium effect on H^+ ion to some extent though some error may creep into the results from (a) liquid-junction potentials of uncertain magnitude, (b) changes in the sensitivity of the glass electrode and (c) solute-solvent interactions.

It is known that the small error in the measurement of H^+ ion concentrations will have profound effect on the K_a values.

In view of the limitations described above, we prefer to use the theoretically calculated H^+ ion concentrations.

The dissociation constants for the reaction $Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons Fe^{2+} + 3 n-Ph$ have been calculated using the relation $K = K_a \times K_T^{4,5}$.

The molar absorptivities of the nitroferroin complex in MeOH-H₂O and EtOH-H₂O mixtures (Table 1) do not show any systematic variation and cannot be correlated with other data obtained similar to those observed in case of bipyridyl and phenanthroline complexes.

The pK_T values of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline, as determined by Ram, Mandal and Lahiri⁹ show that the pK_T value decreases slowly with increasing organic solvent and passes through a maximum near about 60-80 wt% of organic solvents. The changes in pK values can be ascribed to greater solubility of 5-n-Ph and the differences in solvation of 5-n-PhH⁺ and H⁺ ions. The introduction of nitro-substituent increases the dissociation of n-PhH⁺.

The alcohols markedly increase the dissociation constant of the ligand and consequently that of the complex.

The pK_a for the reaction (2) shows a slight decrease with the introduction of alcohol but it gradually increases with increase in organic solvents i.e. ΔG_t is positive. But the ΔpK_t or ΔG_t values for the reaction (3) are negative indicating the spontaneity of reaction (3). It indicates that $Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+}$ is relatively unstable in alcohol-water mixtures. The reaction (2) is governed by the solvational properties of $Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+}$, H⁺, Fe^{2+} and n-PhH⁺ whereas the reaction (3) is governed by the solvational properties $Fe(n-Ph)_3^{2+}$, Fe^{2+} and the solubility of n-Ph.

In view of the inadequate knowledge of the solvational properties of ions in mixed solvents, nothing specific can be said. Though the electrostatic free-energy of transfer is generally regarded to be the same for "isoelectric" reactions, it is not necessarily true in view of the differences of radii-values of the reactants and the products and the low values of the dielectric constants in mixed solvents.

It is apparent that the variation of structural properties of the solvent systems, i.e., solvent-solvent and ion-solvent interactions are primarily responsible for the variation of pK values^{1,5}. The importance of solute-solvent interactions is observed for the complex concentration dependence of excess thermodynamic functions of mixing of different alcohol-water mixtures arising from the complex interactions of the polar OH groups as well as apolar CH₃- or C₂H₅- groups^{1,6}. Addition of alcohol first increases the three-dimensional polymeric structure of water, structure formation is maximum at about 0.1 mole-fraction of the organic solvent^{1,7}, subsequent addition of alcohol depolymerizes the solvent-structure. Thus, a change in basicity of the solvent-mixtures and other related thermodynamic properties are

TABLE 2—pK VALUES FOR THE REACTION (1), (2) AND (3) IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

Wt% of Mole MeOH	fraction of methanol	$\frac{1}{\epsilon} \times 10^3$	pK _T for reaction (1)	pK _a for reaction (2) using calculated [H ⁺]	pK for reaction (3) using calculated [H ⁺]
0.0	0.0000	1.27	3.22	5.95	15.61
8.0	0.0470	1.33	3.09	6.02	15.29
16.0	0.0968	1.40	2.94	5.93	14.15
25.2	0.1593	1.48	2.82	5.86	13.72
34.4	0.2279	1.57	2.65	5.43	13.38
44.7	0.3126	1.69	2.50	5.83	13.33
54.2	0.3997	1.84	2.30	5.89	12.79
64.1	0.5000	2.01	2.10	6.12	12.42
75.9	0.6392	2.25	1.95	6.51	12.86

TABLE 3—pK VALUES FOR THE REACTIONS (1), (2) AND (3) IN ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

Wt.% of Mole EtOH	fraction of ethanol	$\frac{1}{\epsilon} \times 10^3$	pK _T for reaction (1)	pK _a for reaction (2) using calculated [H ⁺]	pK for reaction (3) using calculated [H ⁺]
8.0	0.033	1.35	3.03	5.88	14.97
16.4	0.071	1.42	2.88	6.31	14.95
25.3	0.117	1.53	2.74	5.81	14.03
34.4	0.170	1.71	2.55	6.28	13.93
44.0	0.235	1.90	2.32	5.56	12.82
54.1	0.315	2.14	2.11	6.48	12.81
64.7	0.418	2.44	1.90	6.65	12.35
76.0	0.556	2.87	1.70	6.87	11.97

expected. Addition of ions also leads to the breakdown of the solvent-structure with the formation of ordered solvation zone and disordered solvation zone with the concomitant enthalpy and entropy changes. There are also breakdown of $\geq N \rightarrow H^+$ and $\geq N \rightarrow Fe^{2+}$ bonds from the tetrahedral and octahedral environments to H^+ ion and Fe^{2+} ion with different tetrahedral and octahedral arrangements, respectively. Thus, the structural changes accompanying these processes together with preferential solvation of ions by water molecules and the ligand by alcohol molecules would lead to the enthalpy and entropy changes. However, due to the compensation of enthalpy and entropy changes, little information is obtained from the simpler free-energy terms.

The ΔpK_T values show that the complex is comparatively more stable in methanol-water than in ethanol-water mixture and the solute-solvent interactions are probably in the order

However, it is desirable to study the role of solvents from other physico-chemical studies such as solubility, viscosity, solvation of ions from nmr, ultrasonic and other measurements so that the different aspects of solution chemistry are known with clarity.

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